

ISic1178

Halaesa honours Gaius Vergilius Balbus, proquaestor

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

base (?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

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Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2019-04-03 - Jonathan Prag revised the file based upon 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Assumed to be from Halaesa (Muratori notes that this is one of two which his own notes record at Nafplió in Greece (!), but both of which should rather be attributed to Sicily, and concludes that this should come from Halaesa).

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

The stone was only seen by Muratori, and he did not provide a description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: unknown mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: unknown mm

Text

1. Γάιον Ούεργίλιον Γαίου υιὸν Βάλβον
2. ἀντιταμίαν [ὁ] δᾶμος τῶν Ἀλαισίνων
3. εὐνοίας ἔνεκεν

Apparatus

Text after CIG (Franz)

Translation (en)

The people of the Halaesini (honour) Gaius Vergilius Balbus, son of Gaius, proquaestor, on account of his good will

Translation (it)

Il popolo degli alesini (onora) Gaio Vergilio Balbo, figlio di Gaio, proquestore, per la sua buona volontà

Commentary

Editors from Franz in CIG onwards have assumed that the definite article must have dropped out in line 2 (whether omitted by accident in the transcription or already invisible on the stone) and restored it, as here. The text has the usual form of a compressed dedicatory honorific typical at Halaesa and ubiquitous in the Hellenistic world. It is however unusual, in comparison to the other Halaesan and Sicilian examples in two respects: firstly, the order of honorand and dedicant is reversed, with the city coming second, the Roman magistrate being named first; and secondly, it omits the reference to the deity in the dative to which the likely statue of the honorand is dedicated (typically, at Halaesa, 'to all the gods', although this is not always present; compare ISic0770 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0770>] , ISic1177 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1177>] , ISic0612 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0612>] , also ISic1176 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1176>]). Both these differences are well attested in wider practice (see e.g. J. Ma, *Statutes and Cities* (Oxford 2013), 25), although they may be indicative of the fact that the honorand is the powerful figure of a Roman magistrate and that the text is a relatively late one (at Halaesa, compare the two lost Latin honorifics: that honouring Scipio (ISic0583 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0583>]), which is second century BC, and uses the accusative for the honorand, in typical Greek form, but where the honorand comes second; and that for Augustus (ISic0582 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0582>]), where the honorand is in dative, in typical Latin practice, but comes first, as here).

Gaius Vergilius Balbus [<http://romanrepublic.ac.uk/person/2267>] was praetor in 62 BC and praetorian governor of Sicily from 61-58 BC. His quaestorship will have been in the early 60s BC, at some point between 69 and 66 BC (Prag 2007: 307, Broughton MRR III (1986), 218). Honours for proquaestors, i.e. an individual whose term of office as quaestor had been extended by one or more years by the Senate, are rare, and usually seem to be for individuals who have in fact temporarily taken on the duties of a full praetorian governor (Badian 1983: 158).

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Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0356 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

- Muratori, Ludovico Antonio 1740. *Novus thesaurus veterum inscriptionum in praecipuis earumdem collectionibus hactenus praetermissarum, collectore Ludovico Antonio Muratorio ... Tomus secundus*. Mediolani. At 1022 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/503496>)
- Castelli, Gabriele Lancillotto, principe di Torremuzza 1753. *Storia di Alesa, antica città di Sicilia*. Palermo. At 145 no.3 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/280757>)
- Castelli, Gabriele Lancillotto, principe di Torremuzza 1769. *Siciliae et objacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio*. Panormus. At 54 cl.5 no.41 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/501350>)
- Castelli, Gabriello Lancillotto, Principe di Torremuzza 1784. *Siciliae et objacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio prolegomenis et notis illustrata, et iterum cum emendationibus, & auctariis evulgata*. Palermo. At 59 cl.5 no.42 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/501762>)
- Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum*. Berlin. At 3.5597
- Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezenberger, A. 1884-1915. *Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften*. Göttingen. At 5204
- Cagnat, R., Toutain, J., Jouguet, P. 1906-1927. *Inscriptiones Graecae ad res Romanas pertinentes*. Paris. At 508
- Badian, E. 1983. The silence of Norbanus. A note on provincial Quaestors under the Republic. *AJPh*. 104: 156-171.. At 158
- Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 180 n.64
- Facella, A. 2006. Alesa Arconidea: ricerche su un'antica città della Sicilia tirrenica. Pisa. At 246-248
- Prag, J.R.W. 2007. Auxilia and gymnasia: a Sicilian model of Roman Republican Imperialism. *Journal of Roman Studies*. 97: 68-100. At 307
- Prestianni Giallombardo, A. M. 2012. Spazio pubblico e memoria civica. Le epigrafi dall'agora di Alesa. In Ampolo, C.(eds.), *Agora greca e agorai di Sicilia*. Pisa. pp. 171-200. At 181 fig.165
- Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.44

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